

METHODS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY GRADE TEACHERS BASED ON STEAM APPROACH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15527903>

Annotation: This article presents the systematization of national and foreign experience on the problem of improving creative competence in primary school teachers, the current state of the didactic system for developing logical, critical and creative thinking in them, and the pedagogical. The aim is to achieve conscious mastery of educational material by applying the acquired theoretical knowledge, practical skills, qualifications and competencies of primary school teachers in new situations, using methods based on modern educational technologies. The article also focuses on developing the creative abilities of primary school teachers, and also reflects on modern forms of education and their importance in the world education system, and discusses the possibilities and current achievements of developing the education system based on the STEAM approach, which is considered one of the modern forms of education. The advantages of using STEAM in the primary education system are to expand the capabilities of primary education teachers through the development of technical and natural science education, based on the establishment of connections between the priorities and networks of the program. This article discusses the organization of questionnaires on the clarification and optimization of education through the STEAM approach and the creation of a logical basis for the seamless integration of theoretical knowledge with practice.

Keywords: primary school teacher, creativity, competence, creative ability, creative competence, method, STEAM approach, education, technology, integration.

Today's rapidly developing and evolving world of education requires, first of all, an innovative and creative approach to the educational process. Innovative creative competence, which directly determines the development and direction of any society in the world, occurs under the influence of creativity and is characterized by an increased need for creativity in every sphere of human activity. In foreign developed countries, including the USA, Canada, Finland, Germany, Russia, Japan, Korea, we can see that educational processes are being implemented on the basis of the creative competence STEAM approach.

As a result of direct observation and in-depth analysis of this situation, the main goal of state policy in the field of education is to reform the current education sector, bring the national education system into line with world education standards, and train modern, highly qualified teachers. On August 23, 2019, during a conversation with public education and higher education officials, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev reflected on the urgent tasks that need to be carried out in the continuous education system, stating that “... education today "to raise the reputation of teachers working in educational institutions, and at the same time, today teachers themselves should also take a new and creative approach to the educational process," a number of ideas were emphasized.

Thus, we can achieve great achievements by applying the most advanced technologies of developed countries in our education sector. One of the advanced technologies in the field of education is STEAM technology.

Primary teachers are able to solve more real-life problems to help students acquire modern knowledge and skills. STEAM science, technology, engineering and mathematics education can help primary teachers better understand concepts, such as problem-solving. However, it remains unclear how to apply an integrative approach in the classroom. There is also a lack of an integrative approach in primary education curricula. Primary education teacher training is often focused on understanding the world through interdisciplinary discrete logical analysis. Primary teachers also need to have extensive training in scientific research, technology, design and engineering to teach practical skills. A review of advanced interdisciplinary educational technologies has allowed us to focus on STEAM education. A study was conducted to examine and evaluate the process of developing teacher competencies and critical thinking in natural sciences. During the research, it is necessary to identify and eliminate interdisciplinary problems of both professional and scientific and practical nature by primary school teachers.

It is known that professional experience is reflected in the quality of integration of knowledge, skills and competencies. However, the assimilation of professional competencies and skills of creative activity by primary school teachers requires not only the integration of practical skills and qualifications, the development of methods and tools for the effective organization of activities as a specialist, but also awareness of the methodology of professional creativity, the development of creative thinking, and the assimilation of personal qualities of a creative nature to a sufficient degree.

In the lesson processes organized using the STEAM approach, the teacher and the student actively participate. Because the manipulation and integration of the real modern environment and its information and communication part, including the implementation of experiments with programmable robotic devices, in the educational activity attracts the learner. In the STEAM program, experiments with elementary school teachers are organized through elementary activities, moving from simple to complex. If this principle is followed, elementary school teachers will have no difficulty organizing difficult experiments and working independently in the laboratory. As STEAM skills are formed in elementary school teachers, the teacher and student will develop a body of intellectual knowledge about existence, the world around us. To fully understand the general essence of the process of developing creative competence in primary school teachers, it is first necessary to understand the meaning of the concepts of “creativity” and “creative approach”. According to Ken Robinson, “creativity is a set of original ideas that have their own value”. Gardner, in his research, explains this concept as follows: “creativity is a practical action carried out by an individual, which must reflect a certain novelty and have a certain practical value.”

From the point of view of Emebile’s approach, creativity means “the possession of a high level of unusual skills along with well-developed knowledge in a certain field.”

Creativity (Latin, English: “create” – creation, “creative” – creator, creator) – describes a person’s readiness to develop new ideas and expresses the meaning of creative ability, which is part of talent as an independent factor. A person’s creativity is manifested in his thinking, communication, feelings, and certain types of activity.

Creativity describes a person as a whole or their specific characteristics, mental acuity. Creativity is also reflected as an important factor of talent. According to the American psychologist P. Torrens, “creativity is the development of a problem or scientific hypothesis; the verification and modification of a hypothesis; the definition of a problem based on the formation of the results of a decision; the effectiveness of the interaction of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem” focuses on having a constant, consistent exchange of ideas about pedagogical achievements.

We have identified the concepts of creative competence, knowledge, skills and qualifications characteristic of primary school teachers from a research point of view. In particular, it was found that creative competence knowledge is a product of cognitive activity of understanding and imagination required to develop a new solution, while creative competence skills, systematized in the human mind, express the degree of rapid and complete implementation of the stages of the mental process in goal-directed creative activity. Creative competence skills refer to the degree to which a person is able to carry out creative activity in a partially automated manner, while understanding only the initial stages of the mental process.

Factors for the development of creative competence activity by primary school teachers should be the basis of educational activity in each subject and each lesson. We believe that creative competence activity covers all aspects of the teacher's and student's activities, and its effective organization ensures the quality of the entire educational process. Familiarity with scientific and technical information plays an important role in the development of creative competence activity. It requires the formation of an important source of innovative ideas and technologies along with the training of qualified primary school teachers. In this work, the concept of creative competence was adopted as a process of activity aimed at creating a product of creative competence as intellectual property based on the integration of students' knowledge, skills and abilities with scientific and technical knowledge and educational-scientific-developmental integration.

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